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IOWA STATE UNIVERSITY

Iowa State University

Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering

Dependable Networking and Computing Lab

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Iowa State University is a public flagship classified as a Research University with very high research activity by the Carnegie Foundation for the Advancement of Teaching, receiving nearly US\$300 million in research grants each year.

The **Dependable Networking and Computing Lab** explores theories, methods, and systems building-blocks for addressing dynamics and uncertainties in networked systems. Presently, we are especially interested in the modeling, algorithmic, and systems issues in wireless sensing and control networks (e.g., those in 5G and beyond) as well as their applications. For instance, as a part of the CPS, NeTS, US Ignite, CC*, and GOALI programs of NSF and in collaboration with industry, we have been investigating field-deployable mechanisms for predictable, real-time wireless networking as well as their integration with SDN and edge/cloud computing infrastructures for mission-critical control and AR/VR applications. Our work has been recognized by the Best Demo Award at the 23rd and 21st NSF GENI Engineering Conference in 2015 and 2014 respectively.

READY FOR:

OPEN IDEAS

x1 CHALLENGE

RESEARCHERS

INNOVATORS

OPEN IDEAS

PROPOSE YOUR OWN IDEA

Submit openly a disruptive idea based on your line of research, product or service. Attract the interest of this US Node.

FOCUS TECHNOLOGY AREAS

AI	Blockchain
Big Data	IoT
5G	Cybersecurity
Cloud/Edge	

KEY APPLICATION SECTORS

Agriculture
Transportation
Smart grid

CHALLENGE #12 - ISU-MR-01

→ Trustworthy, Real-Time Wireless Networking for Control and Mixed-Reality (MR) Systems

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

Develop trustworthy, predictable, ultra-reliable and low-latency wireless network systems for mission-critical, and often-times safety-critical, control and mixed-reality systems in domains such as agriculture, transportation, power grid, and public safety.

OBJECTIVES

Address uncertainties (e.g., wireless channel uncertainties, interference, and attacks) in wireless systems, towards enabling predictable, real-time wireless communication for safety-critical applications.

SKILLS REQUIRED

Passion and background in the design, analysis, and prototyping of real-world advanced wireless systems.

